

DIVINFOOD

Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food

Deliverable D2.2

Guidelines to develop new products and recipes from mild processing

Due date of deliverable: M48

Actual submission date: M49

Start date of the project: May 1st, 2022

Duration: 60 months

Organisation name of lead contractor: Biocivam11

Revision: V3

Dissemination level	
Public - PU	X
Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including Commission Services) - CO	
Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC - CI	

Metadata

CALL	H2020-SFS-2020-2
Topic	SFS-01-2018-2019-2020 - Biodiversity in action: across farmland and the value chain
Project ID	101000383
Project website	www.DIVINFOOD.eu
Document type	Deliverable
Title	Deliverable D2.2 - Guidelines to develop new products and recipes from mild processing
Author(s)	Martin Krier (Biocivam11) Luca Colombo (FIRAB) Jean-François Tedesco (mPmC) Maria Carlota Vaz Patto (UNL) Miriam Zago (CREA) Valérie Stahl, Lysiane Omhover (Aerial, third Party ACTIA) Gwenaelle Jard (EI Purpan-INRAE)
Date of creation	28/03/2026
Version number	V3
Internal reviewers	Jean-François Tedesco (mPmC), Yuna Chiffolleau (INRAE)
Keywords	Mild processing, cereals, legumes, sprouting, fermentation, good practices
Dissemination level	Public – PU

Note: This deliverable was completed a month late in order to improve its presentation and make it easier for stakeholders to use.

To cite this document:

Krier M., Colombo L., Tedesco J.-F., Vaz Patto M. C., Zago M., Stahl V., Omhover L., Jard G., 2026. *Deliverable D2.2- Guidelines to develop new products/recipes from mild processing*. DIVINFOOD H2020 project, report, 16 p. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19163099>.

Executive summary

In a societal context where sustainability, nutritional quality and the naturalness of food are becoming increasingly important, mild processing methods are attracting growing interest. These approaches aim to preserve the sensory, nutritional and functional qualities of food as much as possible, whilst ensuring its safety and nutritional quality. However, processors are not necessarily familiar with these techniques. This document provides guidelines on several mild processing techniques applied to Neglected and Underutilised Crops (NUCs), namely minor cereals and legumes, developed as part of the DIVINFOOD project. It aims to facilitate the implementation or optimisation of these still little-known techniques with a view to more sustainable food systems that prioritise health and the environment, in line with the principles of agroecology. This document is intended for stakeholders likely to be interested in developing such processes as part of their activities: farmers, processors, artisans, restaurant chefs (in the private or public sector), etc. The detailed examples provided relate to sprouting, fermentation and stone-milling of cereals and/or legumes. Good practices are highlighted for each technique, including those relating to the management and control of safety risks. A summary of the benefits and key points to watch regarding the mild processing techniques is provided at the end of the document.

Guidelines to develop new products and recipes from mild processing

Introduction

In a societal context where sustainability, nutritional quality and the naturalness of food are becoming increasingly important, mild processing methods are attracting growing interest. These approaches aim to preserve the sensory, nutritional and functional qualities of food as much as possible, whilst ensuring its safety and nutritional quality. Unlike intensive processing methods, mild food processing favours moderate processing conditions that do not subject food to high external stresses (high temperatures and pressures, additives, pasteurisation, flavour enhancers, high mineral and sugar content).

These new approaches stand in contrast to the processing methods most commonly used in the food industry today. That is to say, the excessive use of food additives and flavour enhancers to serve marketing interests (creating appetising and convenient products), often at the expense of nutritional qualities, or even at the expense of health.

This document provides guidelines on several mild processing techniques applied to Neglected and Underutilised Crops (NUCs), namely minor cereals and legumes, as part of the DIVINFOOD project. It aims to facilitate the implementation or optimization of these still less well-known techniques in the perspective of a more sustainable food system that prioritises health and the environment, in line with the principles of agroecology. This document is intended for stakeholders who may be interested in developing such processes as part of their activities: farmers, processors, artisans, restaurant chefs (in the private or public sector), etc.

If you would like to find out more, access webinar replays or chat with users and experts of mild processing, visit the community of practice page on the DIVINFOOD website and join in!

<https://divinfood.eu/community-in-practice/>

What is mild processing ?

Mild processing refers to processing methods that rely on the natural mechanisms inherent in food (microorganisms, enzymes, plant or animal metabolism) or on gentle physical processes (drying, salting, natural acidification, fermentation, sprouting, etc.).

Abel et al., 2022; FAO, 2022

It is essential to preserve the sensory and nutritional qualities of agricultural raw materials, particularly to meet consumer demand for higher-quality food – both in terms of taste and nutrition – without resorting to potentially harmful chemical processes or causing harm to the environment.

→ Mild processing methods help to better preserve vitamins, bioactive compounds, colour, texture and flavour. For example, the use of non-thermal or low-temperature processes helps to limit the breakdown of heat-sensitive vitamins.

→ Mild processing methods can serve as alternatives to conventional pasteurisation or sterilisation for food preservation, as these can compromise the quality of the raw material.

→ Mild processing methods meet the need for resource efficiency (low energy or water consumption) and limit external pollutants (additives, pesticides, heavy metal residues, etc.).

Mild processing methods can therefore be considered a relevant approach to incorporate into professional projects, particularly to meet growing consumer expectations and address environmental challenges.

The application of mild processes to Neglected and Underutilised Crops (NUCs) is particularly relevant, as it helps to promote these little-known crops whilst preserving their nutritional, sensory and environmental qualities, thereby enhancing their appeal to consumers.

Examples of mild processing methods developed in the DIVINFOOD Project

Here is a non-exhaustive list of gentle processing methods developed by local stakeholders as part of the DIVINFOOD project for a range of minor cereals and/or legumes. These methods have often been developed through collaboration between artisans, farmers and researchers, with consumer testing carried out wherever possible. These are successful experiments that can be implemented in the field and are of real interest for the promotion of NUCs. This list sets out the types of mild processing techniques that may be considered for the processing of minor cereals and/or legumes.

Thermal processes

Thermal processes falling within the category of mild processing techniques include low-temperature cooking, low-temperature drying, solar drying, etc.

These techniques help preserve nutritional and flavour qualities. They are also of considerable interest for improving shelf life. In particular, they help prevent the oxidation and degradation of sensitive food components such as vitamins, antioxidants and aromatic compounds.

Germination/soaking processes

Sprouting involves soaking cereals or legumes in water at room temperature (between 20°C and 30°C). This process aims to trigger the development of the grains into young shoots. This transformation leads to changes in the nutritional characteristics of the products, which are generally beneficial for human consumption, particularly in terms of improved nutritional and sensory qualities. The improvement in nutritional quality is reflected in particular by a reduction in carbohydrate (sugar) content and improved digestibility of cereals and legumes.

Sprouted foods are then often subjected to further processing such as gentle drying, gentle cooking or fermentation.

Example: Soaking einkorn and rivet wheat for the production of bulgur

Einkorn and rivet wheat are ancient varieties of wheat, native to the Mediterranean region and Europe, which were cultivated during many years. They were subsequently gradually replaced by soft wheat and durum wheat, considered more productive. In recent years, however, einkorn and rivet wheat have seen a resurgence in interest, as they appear to be more resistant to stress (drought, disease, etc.) and offer yields that, whilst more modest, are more stable and consistent. Processing them further enhances their beneficial effects. Sprouting enhances their intrinsic nutritional qualities whilst forming part of a mild and sustainable processing method. Soaking is one of the key stages in the production of bulgur.

Experimentation of rivet wheat bulgur
(Purpan/INRAE-DIVINFOOD)

Fermentation processes

Fermentation improves the nutritional quality of food. The microorganisms used in fermentation processes contribute to the synthesis of beneficial compounds, improve protein digestibility and help reduce certain undesirable or toxic compounds present in food.

The fermentation of cereals and legumes has numerous applications and uses. Depending on the processes used, it can serve various purposes, such as improving the nutritional, sensory or preservation qualities of products.

- From a culinary perspective, the fermentation of legumes and cereals is used in condiments (for example, gochujang chilli paste), to flavour ingredients and dishes (miso, soy sauce, etc.).
- Fermentation intended for direct consumption is widely used in the production of alcohol, snacks (e.g. tempeh snacks) and dishes made from fermented cereals.

Here are some examples of fermentation processes and the products that can be obtained: lactic acid fermentation (cheese, yoghurt, kefir, sourdough, pickles, etc.), alcoholic fermentation (bread, fermented drinks) and fungal fermentation (tempeh, miso, cheese).

Examples of fermentation processes developed in DIVINFOOD

Grass pea is a legume grown mainly in Africa, Asia and certain Mediterranean regions. Valued for its high resistance to drought and harsh climatic conditions, it is an important source of plant-based protein.

Tempeh is produced through a process of fermenting grains to produce a compact cake, resulting in a food rich in protein, fibre and nutrients.

Producing tempeh from grass pea opens up new possibilities for this still underutilised legume.

Fried grass pea tempeh chips

Experimentation of tempeh with grass pea (UNL/CookLab/ADECA - DIVINFOOD)

Experimentation of dairy-like products with white lupin (CREA-FIRAB-DIVINFOOD)

White lupin is increasingly recognised as a valuable source of plant-based protein, offering a more sustainable alternative to animal protein. In addition to protein, lupins also contain fats, dietary fibre, minerals and vitamins. Their use in the food industry holds promise for promoting healthier diets and more sustainable food systems.

An experiment carried out at DIVINFOOD aimed to develop dairy-style products, as well as formulations and recipes using white lupin as a raw material. More specifically, the products were fermented using selected lactic acid bacteria to improve their nutritional and organoleptic quality and, potentially, to reduce or minimise the levels of antinutritional compounds (such as phytic acid and alkaloids) typically found in lupins.

Mechanical processes

Mild mechanical processes involve the application of moderate physical forces, without significant heat input or the use of chemical solvents. They enable the raw material to be processed whilst preserving its structure, nutrients and sensory qualities as much as possible. They often constitute the first stage in the processing of plant-based materials, particularly NUCs. Mechanical processes include:

Manual or gentle hydraulic press

- Used to extract juice, oils, or pulp.
- Operates at low pressure, limiting heating and oxidation
- Suitable for seeds, fruits, vegetables, or legumes
- Advantages: simplicity, low energy consumption, good process control
→ Examples of uses: vegetable juices, artisanal oils, pressed purées.

Astrié mill and granite stone from a cereal producer involved in DIVINFOOD trials

Slow-grinding mill/millstone

- Low-speed grinding to prevent temperature rise
- Preserves aromas, sensitive lipids, and fiber structure
- Suitable for seeds, grains, dry or sprouted legumes
→ Examples of uses: whole meal flours, vegetable pastes, seed purées.

Use of Astrié mills (stone millstones) for einkorn and rivet wheat:

This type of mill, which operates on the principle of compressing the grains between granite millstones, produces a flour with remarkable and recognised nutritional qualities. For example, the T80/T100/T110 flour obtained in this way is richer in fibre and protein, whilst being lower in carbohydrates.

Milling using a gentle compression method effectively separates the fibrous elements (cellulose from the bran) from the starch. As with all millstones, and unlike roller mills (conventional mills), the wheat germ is pressed and incorporated into the starch grains, whilst the natural abrasion of the granite ensures the bran is ground and the proteins extracted. Astrié mills are particularly well-suited to processing ancient grains such as einkorn and rivet wheat.

Find others examples in the DIVINFOOD project

There is a wide variety of recipes and products made from cereals and/or legumes that can be produced using gentle processing methods. You will find several of these products and recipes in deliverable D2.1 of the DIVINFOOD project: <https://zenodo.org/records/15113394>

Develop mild processing techniques

Establish your manufacturing process

Once the design of the final product has been finalised, a production plan can be put in place. To illustrate this section of the guide, we will examine the different steps of the manufacturing process. We will draw on examples of mild processing methods that have been developed as part of the DIVINFOOD project.

Step 1: Identify human and material resources

- Set up your production area: determine the space required to install production and storage equipment, and organise the space to optimise logistics.
- Identify the equipment to be purchased, as well as the technical and methodological tools needed to implement the gentle process(es) required for manufacturing the product or recipe.
- Determine the skills required to carry out production. This step is essential to ensure that managers have the necessary knowledge to supervise the process and guarantee the quality of the final product.
- Identify suppliers: raw material if you are not a farmer, as well as the inputs required to carry out the manufacturing process.

Example of the process for making bulgur with einkorn and rivet wheat:

Required materials:

- Sieves
- Incubator
- Steam Oven
- Dryer
- Crusher

Required skills:

- Knowledge of cereal germination.
- Technical skills in the use of tools.
- Knowledge of food safety risks related to moisture content in products.

The space and human resources required for this production can vary greatly (micro production unit for a kitchen / medium-sized production unit / artisanal / quasi-industrial production unit with high volumes and several machines).

Step 2: Define a production process and fully understand each stage

Defining a production process is important because it enables you to visualise and organise all the key stages of product manufacturing. For the sake of transparency and risk management, this approach is also crucial for anticipating and quickly resolving any manufacturing issues that may arise. Here are some examples of processes tested as part of DIVINFOOD.

Example of the production of bulgur with einkorn

1- Cleaning and Sorting

In a sieve put sorted and dehulled einkorn

2- Soaking

In an incubator put 1 kg of einkorn for 2kg of water.

During 3h30, at 55°C

The objective of soaking is to achieve a moisture content of 45%. (Main step to obtain the essential characteristics of bulgur)

3 - Pre-Cooking

In a steam oven, pre-cook the soaked einkorn.

During 45min, at 100°C. To achieve a humidity level of 40%

Pre-cooking involves partially cooking the grains. This partial cooking softens the grains and makes them easier to crush or grind later.

4 - Drying

In Dryer - Dry the einkorn

During 15h30, at 60 to 20°C to achieve a humidity level of 10%

There are several objectives to drying: it removes excess moisture and ensures better preservation (eliminates micro-organisms and limits product deterioration)

5 - Crushing

In Crusher - This step involves grinding the einkorn grains to obtain fragments of different sizes. Crushing helps transform the grain into a more easily consumable form, improving digestibility and allowing for faster and more uniform cooking.

6 - Classification Sieving

Einkorn fragments are passed through sieves with different mesh sizes, allowing the particles to be separated according to their size.

1 to 2 mm (desired grain size)

The purpose of sieving is to control the particle size of bulgur by removing unwanted fragments and obtaining fractions of the appropriate size.

Bulgur mild processing (Purpan-INRAE-DIVINFOOD)

Example of grass pea fermentation

1- Selection of the raw material

Be aware of the quality of the grass pea seeds: it should not contain bugs, or any kind of soil residues.

2 - Soaking

This step influences the fungi growth and the final product quality.

Soak overnight, under room temperature (20-25°C) to promote LAB and acidify the grass pea before inoculation with the fungi, and guarantee that other microorganisms present will not grow.

3- Cooking

Use undercooked seeds. If you overcook grass pea, you will 1) get too soft grains and loose the structure of tempeh 2) make single sugar more available and increase the probability of spoiling the product before the mold is able to grow.

If you overcook the grass pea seeds you will increase the probability of spoiling the product before the mold was able to grow.

Fermenting grass pea in a plastic bag - a joint experiment between LL Geap-Port and Bean-Lyon (UNL/CookLab/ADECA - DIVINFOOD)

4 - Fermentation

In a plastic food bag, use the right amount of fungi starter and ensure an even distribution to achieve uniform fermentation.

Add vinegar to help to acidify the grains.

Control environmental conditions (temperature, humidity, and oxygen). Uncontrolled conditions can result in uneven growth or spoilage.

Too much humidity increases the probability of spoiling the product before the mold is able to grow.

Remove the excess of water by drying between paper towels.

The mold needs oxygen to grow, so the bag should be pinched all over.

Try not to leave big empty spaces in the bag, try to compact the seeds against the bag walls. If you do not compact the seeds in the bag, you will get a loose/less-structured tempeh and you will have difficulties in slicing the tempeh. If you make big holes in the bag the mold will overgrow and became dark in those places and the outside part of the product (although still safe) won't be so nicely white.

Put it at 33-37°C for 36 to 48h to promote mold grow.

5 - Conditioning and storing

After the mold growth put in the fridge if you are going to use it in the next days or freeze it.

Example of the production of a dairy-like product using white lupin

1- Soaking

Soak lupin seeds in water

Soak for three days, rinsing repeatedly

2- Cooking

Cook for 1 hour. Pasteurise the mixture at 70°C for 20 minutes. This step is important for controlling health risks.

3 - Preparation and fermentation

Grind the lupin mixture

Add the selected starter cultures (in case of this experience: *L. acidophilus* and *S. thermophiles*, chosen because they showed the most pleasant aroma). In general, it is important to carry out several trials with different tests using different selected lactic acid bacteria in order to obtain the best possible final product.

Ferment at 37°C for 24 hours

Add vegetable oil and salt, mix to obtain a homogeneous emulsion

4 - Conditioning

Shape and drain at 8–10°C for three days to obtain a firm matrix

Spices and aromatic herbs can be added to improve the taste and aroma, with satisfactory sensory results.

Step 3: Ensure the quality and food safety of your products

As with other processing techniques, food producers must implement good hygiene practices and apply the HACCP system to control microbiological risks. Microbiological self-monitoring plans and stability studies should be used to determine the presence of pathogenic bacteria and the behaviour of undesirable microorganisms in NUC raw materials and/or food products during storage and the sales period. The presence of undesirable microorganisms depends on the type of processing method, the food formulation, the physicochemical characteristics (pH, moisture content, natural organic acid content, presence of fermentation-relevant microbial flora), packaging conditions (type of atmosphere: air, modified atmosphere, vacuum) and storage and sales conditions (temperature, duration), as well as the shelf life of the food. Undesirable microorganisms include pathogenic bacteria, spoilage flora and hygiene indicator bacteria (European Regulation 2073/2005).

The table below sets out the key elements and good practices to be followed to ensure the safety of products produced using mild processing techniques.

	Microbial food safety risks	Key points to keep in control Impact of parameters	Good practices
RAW MATERIAL - cereals - legumes	A raw material can be a source of microbial contamination (spoilage microorganisms, pathogenic bacteria, hygiene indicator microorganisms).	Good and safe production conditions	Storage conditions : clean, dry storage areas, storage temperature threshold, packaging of raw materials if necessary
MILD PROCESSING TECHNIQUES			
THERMAL TREATMENT a) Low T°C/duration cooking b) drying of raw materials - low temperature drying - solar drying	a) no destruction of pathogenic bacteria; no reduction of the microbial population responsible for spoilage and hygiene b) high moisture content (%), high water activity (water available for the growth of microorganisms in food) allow the growth of the undesirable microorganisms	a) efficient temperature level / duration b) efficient drying and hygiene of the environment (solar drying) allow the inhibition or elimination of undesirable microorganisms	Keep under control Traceability Keep under control e.g, food threshold of 10% humidity
GERMINATION/ SOAKING PROCESS a) soaking cereal grains, legumes in water (e.g room T°C 20-30°C) b) sprouted foods and additional process: *gentle cooking ** gentle drying	a) Soaking: the levels of temperature and water provide ideal conditions for the growth of microorganisms if the process is prolonged. b) additional process: - no destruction of pathogenic bacteria; no reduction of the microbial population responsible for spoilage and hygiene - growth of the undesirable microorganisms: moisture content (%), water activity (food water available) too high	a) Good hygiene practices of soaking process step; good water quality b) Keeping under control the gentle cooking or gentle drying	Control of the applied process steps Traceability Keep under control e.g, food threshold of 10% humidity

FERMENTATION PROCESS	Growth of the undesirable microorganisms	Efficient technological microorganisms relevant for fermentation If relevant for the food matrix type: - acidification (decrease in pH of the food) and - final product with low moisture content /low water activity permit the inhibition of pathogens and spoilage flora	Control of fermentation steps: - high population of positive technological microorganisms relevant for fermentation - control of the process parameters : T°C, duration, and associated drying if a relevant process step or not; concentration of natural organics acids
MECHANICAL PROCESS (Astrié Millstones) e.g flour	Growth of the undesirable microorganisms: moisture content (%), water activity (food water available) too high	final product with low moisture content /low water activity Enable the inhibition of pathogens and spoilage flora	Low food moisture content
FINAL FOOD PRODUCT, RECIPE	Growth of microorganisms under storage and sale conditions	Optimisation of the packaging and determination of the use-by-date (refrigerated temperature/duration) or best-before (room temperature/duration)	Good storage conditions: packaging; and storage conditions T°C/duration/ humidity conditions Label on packaging: best -before or use by-date, description of the use by the consumer (to be consumed directly or not, reheating, cooking, etc.)

Benefits of mild processing and key points to watch

Benefits of mild processing techniques	Key points to watch before or during the use of mild processing techniques
<p>Nutritional and qualitative advantages</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Preservation of the nutritional potential of food (preservation of vitamins, improved digestibility, etc.). – Fermentation of legumes and cereals brings value to gastronomy. Fermented products can enhance different cuisines in a positive way <p>Response to underlying trends</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Search for naturalness – Responsible local consumption – Products perceived as healthier and more natural by consumers – Growing interest in fermentation, living foods, homemade products. <p>Diversification of income</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Creation of high value-added products from simple raw materials – Appropriate technique for small-scale processors and short food supply chains <p>Gradual, controlled investment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Possibility of starting small and scaling up – Low dependence on complex technologies <p>Simple, sustainable processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Low energy consumption (natural drying, fermentation). – Few or no additives – Limited food waste and losses – Simplicity of the fermentation process and high quality of the final food product (e.g., fried grass pea tempeh chips) 	<p>Process variability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Knowledge required depending on the process and raw materials used – Need to accept that the final product will not be standardised <p>Niche market</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Not all consumers are sensitive to mild processes – Constant communication effort needed to reach a wide range of consumers <p>Safety control</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Pay close attention to the specific risks associated with the mild processing technique used

Conclusion

For stakeholders wishing to develop food processing, mild processing methods represent a concrete and relevant opportunity. By drawing on natural processes such as fermentation, sprouting, gentle drying or low-temperature cooking, these methods enable the creation of high value-added products whilst preserving the intrinsic qualities of the raw materials. They thus provide a framework particularly well suited to artisanal, local and sustainable approaches.

Combining mild processing with neglected and underutilised crops (NUCs) further enhances the appeal of these approaches. It enables the utilisation of plant resources that are often local, resilient and nutritionally rich, whilst meeting growing consumer demand for plant-based, minimally processed and meaningful foods. For small-scale food producers, this combination provides a powerful means of differentiation, both economically and in social and environmental terms.

However, the success of such a project depends on certain key conditions. The control of safety risks, the acquisition of specific technical skills, and rigorous production organisation are essential. Furthermore, consumer education and transparency play a central role: explaining the mild processes, their benefits and their limitations is essential for building trust and justifying the value of the products on offer.

Ultimately, committing to mild processing is not merely a technical alternative to industrial processing, but a long-term strategic choice. For small-scale food producers, these processes pave the way for more resilient business models, rooted in local communities and capable of reconciling economic viability, respect for life and a response to current societal expectations.

References

Abel N., Rotabakk B.T., Lerfall J., 2022. Mild processing of seafood—a review. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Sciences and Food Safety*, 21, 340–370. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12876>.

FAO, 2022. *CODEX ALIMENTARIUS COMMISSION. General principles of food hygiene (CXC 1-1969, Rev. 2022)* https://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius/shproxy/en/?lnk=1&url=https%253A%252F%252Fworkspace.fao.org%252Fsites%252Fcodex%252Fstandards%252FCXC%2B1-1969%252FCXC_001e.pdf

Giacomella L., Rowe T., Mathijs R., Vranken L., 2025. Environmental impacts of local consumption, short supply chains, mild processing, and small scale production: A comparison of fruit juice alternatives. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 501, 145318, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.145318>.

Nkhata S. G., Kamau E. H., Ayua E., Shingiro J. B., 2018. Fermentation and germination improve nutritional value of cereals and legumes through activation of endogenous enzymes. *Food Science & Nutrition*, 6(7), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fsn3.846>